

Minimum Phase Filter Bank with reduced delay and bandwidth extension flexibility for Audiogram matching in Digital Hearing Aids

Mahesh V V¹, Suresh Kumar A V², Deepthi P M³ Ratheesh T⁴

^{1,2,3,4}College of Engineering Trikaripur, Kasaragod, Kerala

Abstract

Digital Hearing aid design requires a set of filters that gives reasonable audiogram matching for a specific case of hearing loss. Many a fixed and reconfigurable filter banks are reported for different types of sound wave decomposition plans. But the delay and hardware complexity of these structures are relatively large for a compact hearing aid system. In this paper, a minimum phase constrained least square finite impulse response filter bank with reduced group delay and low hardware complexity is proposed. Minimum phase FIR filter shows least passband group delay in the group of stable filters with the same magnitude response characteristics and the coefficients required for filter is only half of that of the prototype finite impulse response filter. Low group delay greatly influence the envelope fidelity, which is a prime factor in determining the intelligibility of speech. Multiplications per sample is considerably reduced in this method and is more suitable for systems where the spectra of desired and noise signals are overlapped. Filter coefficient decimation method is used to vary the band edge frequencies of the filters to make the system dynamic to adapt the changes in audiogram pattern which can happen in future by aging of the user. Synthesis results presented supports the theoretical claims in the proposed design.

Keywords— Minimum phase filters; constrained least square filters; finite impulse response filter bank; coefficient decimation; audiogram

1. INTRODUCTION

Hearing aids basically pick up sound from the environment, make it louder and intelligible and play it to the ear. Filter bank plays an important role in selecting and processing the audio signals picked up by the microphone. Filter bank act as the primary structural tool for processing sound, it slices the incoming sound in to multiple frequency bands, allowing the device to treat different parts of sound spectrum independently. Most people with hearing loss don't lose hearing equally across all frequencies. Filter bank amplifies the signals at different levels of volume for each band to compensate the raised hearing thresholds. The digital hearing aid Filter banks can be classified as uniform and non-uniform Filter banks [1-6]. Nonuniform Filter banks are preferred because nonuniform bands mimic the human ear's

logarithmic nature, offering more precision at lower frequencies where the speech quality is most critical. Delays of the order of 10 ms in the device will result disturbing effect for hearing aid users. Hardware requirement, power consumption and delay are the critical parameters for the design of a compact digital hearing aid.

Uniform and nonuniform filters are generally used for the design filter banks in digital hearing aids. Nonuniform filter banks suits better as human ear shows nonuniform frequency resolution properties. Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) Filter bank has low computation complexity but filter bank with Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filter is a better choice due to linear phase characteristic, regular structure and stability of the system. Design and implementation of low-power ANSI S1.11 filter bank structure for digital hearing aids is reported in [1]. Long group delay and stringent filter parameters are the main drawbacks of this system. Customer will be disturbed if the hearing aid delay is more than 10 ms. FIR reconfigurable filter bank with less computational complexity is presented in [2] in which interpolation, decimation and frequency response masking methods are used. Here the hardware complexity is reduced at the expense of longer delay, greater than 20ms. Long delays will cause many issues such as the difference between hearing aid generated and direct received sound, etc.

A reconfigurable filter bank with nonlinear characteristics is proposed in [3] by Huang et al. Variable bandwidth digital filter for hearing aid application with Farrow structure is proposed in [4], in which Canonic Signed Digit (CSD) arithmetic precision is compromised to save hardware. In this case, additional accumulator circuitry is required to change tunable factor value and which will result further increase in complexity of the system. A reconfigurable filter bank using linear phase filter symmetry property and fractional interpolation is reported in [5]. A nonuniform modified Discrete Fourier Transform (MDFT) filter bank is suggested in [6] in which different filter orders are used for different bands. A filter bank with constrained least square (CLS) FIR architecture for audiogram matching in digital hearing aids is presented in [7], in which multiplier requirement is large as the order of filter is high. Fractional interpolation technique is used to design filter banks in [8]. In this method hardware complexity is reduced but the delay is increased up to 12.9 ms. Reconfigurable filter bank for digital hearing aid applications with IoT is reported in [9]. Cosine modulation and Frequency warping techniques are used for the filter bank design in [10]. Delay and Hardware complexity are comparatively low in this design.

From literature review, it is clear that it is hard to trade off between delay and hardware complexity of filter banks for hearing aid devices. In this work, a stable minimum phase filter derived from constrained least square (CLS) FIR filter, is proposed. In a minimum phase filter, the number of coefficients is only half of that of the FIR filter. So hardware requirement of the filter is reduced without any effect on magnitude response characteristics. Coefficient decimation method is used to extend the bandwidth of individual filters.

Since all poles of the system are always inside the unit circle, Minimum phase filters are inherently stable. Minimum phase filter's passband group delay is very much small compared to that of linear phase FIR filter with the same characteristics. This property of the filter helps to preserve the envelope fidelity of speech signal. In a noisy environment, envelope fidelity is an important factor in determining the intelligibility and quality of speech [11]. Minimum phase filter exhibit small variations in phase in the passband but studies in psychoacoustics have reported that the sensitivity of human ear to such small phase distortions is very low. Experiments conducted by Lipshitz et al, reported in [12] states that such minute phase variations on speech signals and normal music are not at all audible by humans. The filter bank structures are synthesized using Cadence Encounter(R) RTL compiler v11.10 software. Matlab software is used to simulate the filter bank response.

The paper is organized as follows. An overview of minimum phase constrained least square FIR filters is given in Section II. Hearing loss and audiogram are discussed in Section III, Filter bank structure implementation and audiogram matching are presented in Section IV, performance evaluation is reported in Section V. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

2. MINIMUM PHASE CONSTRAINED LEAST SQUARE FILTER

2.1 CONSTRAINED LEAST SQUARE FILTER

In Constrained least square FIR filter, it is possible to design FIR filters without explicitly specifying transition widths for the magnitude response. This approach is more suitable for the situations where signal information and noise appear together in the same frequency band. Upper and lower thresholds for maximum allowable ripple in the magnitude response of the filter are defined in this technique [13-15]. Here, least square error minimization technique is applied not only to specific bands but over the whole frequency range of the filter response. The overall error minimization includes areas of discontinuity in the ideal filter response. The integral square error includes the region around cut off frequency and avoids Gibb's phenomenon without using windowing operation. The frequency response of FIR filter can be represented as

$$H(\omega) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} h(n)e^{-j\omega n} \tag{1}$$

If $h(n) = h(N - 1 - n)$, then $H(\omega)$ has linear phase and can be written as

$$H(\omega) = C(\omega)e^{-jM\omega} \tag{2}$$

where $C(\omega)$ is the real valued amplitude, and $M = \frac{(N-1)}{2}$ for filter of length N . For symmetric odd length filters $C(\omega)$ can be represented as

$$C(\omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c(0) + \sum_{n=1}^M c(n) \cos n\omega \tag{3}$$

Where the impulse response coefficients $h(n)$, in terms of the cosine coefficients $c(n)$ are

$$h(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} c(M - n) & \text{for } 0 \leq n \leq M - 1 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} c(0) & \text{for } n = M \\ \frac{1}{2} c(n - M) & \text{for } M + 1 \leq n \leq N - 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

Let $D(\omega)$ be the desired amplitude of an ideal lowpass filter. Approximating this discontinuous function by the cosine polynomial $C(\omega)$ is the fundamental filter design problem.

The approximation error can be written as

$$E(\omega) = D(\omega) - C(\omega) \tag{5}$$

The primary measures of approximation used in filter design are

i) The weighted integral square error is given by

$$\|E(\omega)\|_2 = \left(\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\pi W(\omega) (C(\omega) - D(\omega))^2 d\omega \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \tag{6}$$

ii)The weighted Chebyshev error is given by

$$\|E(\omega)\|_\infty = \max_{\omega \in [0, \pi]} |W(\omega)(C(\omega) - D(\omega))| \tag{7}$$

where $W(\omega)$ is a nonnegative error weighting function. The simplest method to design optimal FIR filters is to minimize the term $\|C(\omega) - D(\omega)\|_2$.

The CLS FIR filter design minimizes the unweighted integral square error with the constraint that local minima and maxima of $C(\omega)$ lie within the specified lower and upper bound functions $K_L(\omega)$ and $K_U(\omega)$. The lower and upper bound functions are given by

$$K_L(\omega) = \begin{cases} 1 - \delta_p & \text{for all } \omega \in [0, \omega_p] \\ -\delta_s & \text{for all } \omega \in [\omega_p, \pi] \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

$$K_U(\omega) = \begin{cases} 1 + \delta_p & \text{for all } \omega \in [0, \omega_p] \\ \delta_s & \text{for all } \omega \in [\omega_p, \pi] \end{cases} \tag{9}$$

where δ_p and δ_s are the maximum allowed deviations in the passband and stopband. This method of filter design is more suitable for situation where the maximum peak error size is to be controlled and the input signals to be filtered have energy in the transition band.

2.2 MINIMUM PHASE CONSTRAINED LEAST SQUARE FILTER

Higher order Linear Phase FIR filter has narrow transition band and has very long group delay which is proportional to the filter order. In hearing aid applications, such a long delay is not at all favorable. By the minor relaxation in linear phase characteristics, design of FIR filter with lower order can be possible. This will in turn reduce the overall group delay and also reduce the cost by saving the number of multipliers required for the filter bank. Minimum phase filter group delay has the smallest value among the family of filters with the same magnitude response characteristics. A stable causal filter is treated as minimum phase filter if all of its zeros are inside the unit circle [13]. Consider a FIR transfer function of degree M

$$H(z) = \sum_{n=0}^M h(n) z^{-n} \tag{10}$$

The mirror image polynomial of H(z) is given by

$$\hat{H}(z) = z^{-M}H(z^{-1}) = \sum_{n=0}^M h(M-n)z^{-n} \tag{11}$$

The zeros of $\hat{H}(z)$ are reciprocal to that of H(z). As a result

$$K(z) = H(z)\hat{H}(z) = z^{-M}H(z)H(z^{-1}) \tag{12}$$

K(z) has zeros with mirror image symmetry in z plane and is thus a Type I linear phase transfer function with order 2M. K(z) has double zeros on the unit circle and is thus factorizable to H(z) and $\hat{H}(z)$. From the equation (12), the magnitude squared function can be represented as

$$|H(e^{j\omega})|^2 = K(\omega) \tag{13}$$

Amplitude response of K(z) is thus non negative. It is also clear that, K(ω) has double zeros on [0,π] interval as K(z) has double zeros on the unit circle. Based on this logic a minimum phase filter can be obtained by using the following procedure [16, 17].

Step1: Design a Type I linear phase FIR transfer function E(z) of degree 2M, with the amplitude response $\hat{E}(\omega)$ specifications

$$1 - \delta_p(E) \leq \hat{E}(\omega) \leq 1 + \delta_p(E) \quad \text{for } \omega \in [0, \omega_p]$$

$$-\delta_s(E) \leq \hat{E}(\omega) \leq \delta_s(E) \quad \text{for } \omega \in [\omega_s, \pi]$$

E(z) has only a single unit circle zero .

Step 2: Determination of the linear phase transfer function

$$K(z) = \delta_s(E) z^{-M} + E(z) \tag{14}$$

Its amplitude response $\hat{K}(\omega)$ satisfies the relation

$$1 + \delta_s(E) - \delta_p(E) \leq \hat{K}(\omega) \leq 1 + \delta_s(E) + \delta_p(E) \quad \text{for } \omega \in [0, \omega_p]$$

$$0 \leq \hat{K}(\omega) \leq 2\delta_s(E) \quad \text{for } \omega \in [\omega_s, \pi]$$

It is evident that, K(z) has double zeros in the stop band along with all other zeros situated with a mirror image symmetry. Thus K(z) can be expressed as

$$K(z) = z^{-M}H(z)H(z^{-1}) \tag{15}$$

Here H(z) is a minimum phase FIR transfer function which contains the zeros of K(z) that are inside unit circle and one from each of the double zeros of K(z) on the unit circle.

Step3: Use spectral factorization to determine H(z) from K(z).

In the direct method, minimum phase filter is obtained by selecting the zeros of K(z) that are inside the unit circle The pass band ripple $\delta_p(E)$ and the stop band ripple $\delta_s(E)$ of E(z) have to ensure that the specified pass band ripple δ_p and stop band ripple δ_s of H(z) are satisfied accurately. It can be shown that

$$\delta_p(E) = \sqrt{1 + \frac{\delta_p}{1 + \delta_s}} - 1 \tag{16}$$

$$\delta_s(E) = \sqrt{\frac{2\delta_s}{1 + \delta_s}} \tag{17}$$

Non linear IIR filters with smaller group delay can be possible, but such filters are not at all stable. The number of coefficients in a minimum phase filter is reduced to half of that of the prototype FIR filter. Smaller group delay can be achieved in the passband region by using stable minimum phase FIR filters with low hardware complexity. Minimum phase filters are always stable because all poles of the system are inside the unit circle. In the proposed design constrained least square FIR Filter is used as the prototype FIR filter to derive minimum phase FIR filter.

2.3 COEFFICIENT DECIMATION METHOD FOR BANDWIDTH EXTENSION

The decimated version of original frequency response is given by the coefficient decimation method (CDM) whose passband width is M times that of prototype filter, where M is integer decimation factor [18-20]. In CDM, every Mth coefficients of prototype filter are grouped together, by removing in between coefficients. The stop band attenuation decreases as the value of M increases, hence M=2 is selected for the filter implementation. Decimated filter bandwidth will be M times that of the original prototype filter. CDM method is suitable for designing discrete tunable filters. The structure of the coefficient decimated filter for M=2 is shown in Figure.1

Fig. 1. Coefficient decimated filter structure

3. AUDIOGRAM AND HEARING LOSS

Audiometric testing is used to measure the hearing ability of a person and a chart of this measurement is known as Audiogram. The softest sound a person can hear at specific audio frequency band is termed as threshold of hearing. Audiogram of a person with normal level of hearing is shown in Figure 2. Here, Y axis represents the ear response measured in decibels (dB) and corresponding frequency in Hertz (Hz) is plotted in X axis. Generally, thresholds upto 20 dB are treated as normal hearing level. Symbols ‘O’ and ‘X’ used in the audiogram represents the response of right ear and left ear respectively. In a standard audiogram, hearing level measurements are usually carried out at octave frequencies (250/500/1k/2k/4k/8k).

Fig. 2 Audiogram for normal hearing

A hearing impaired person’s sensitivity is low at certain frequency bands and this hearing loss is rectified by the

selective amplification of sound signals at the respective band of frequencies. Reference audiograms used in this work are selected from the website of independent hearing aid information source <http://www.earinfo.com>. Response of hearing aid filter bank should match the audiogram of affected patient to compensate the hearing loss by selective amplification of audio signals. Audiograms of mild hearing loss at all frequencies, mild hearing loss at high frequencies and mild to moderate hearing loss at all frequencies are used in this paper for the analysis of hardware complexity, delay and matching error. Matching error is defined as the maximum overall error between filter bank response and the audiogram of a specific hearing loss case. Matching error 3dB is considered as the maximum tolerable limit, because psycho acoustical studies have shown that [11,12], people are generally not sensitive to errors less than 3dB.

4 CLS FIR FILTER BANK AND AUDIOGRAM MATCHING

CLS FIR filter of order $n = 32$, $\delta_p = 10^{-5}$, $\delta_s = 10^{-5}$ is used as the prototype filter for the design of minimum phase filter bank structure. The smooth transition band characteristic of minimum phase CLS FIR filter enables to reduce filter order and number of bands required for audiogram matching. The individual band widths of 7 filters used for filter bank design are shown in Table 1. Matlab software is used to simulate the filter bank response. Frequency response of low pass minimum phase CLS FIR filter with cut off frequency 2 kHz is shown in Figure 3. Sampling frequency used for the filter design is 16 kHz and maximum pass band group delay of the filter is 0.4935 ms. Group delay shows a slight variation from 5 to 8 samples in the pass band as shown in Figure 4. But this minor phase variations do not affect the hearing perception.

Fig. 3. Frequency responses of prototype and decimated (M=2) Minimum phase low pass filter.

Table 1: Frequency bands used

Hearing loss	No. of bands	Bandwidth (Hz)
Mild hearing loss at all frequencies.	7	400,1200,2000,2200,1800,1300, 1100
Mild hearing loss at high frequencies.	7	800,2100,1500,1200,1600,2400,1700
Mild to moderate hearing loss at low frequencies.	7	600,800,1100,3300,2100,2400, 900

Number of coefficient multiplications required is only 17 for minimum phase filter derived from the CLS FIR filter with order 32. Pass band group delay and number of multipliers required for the proposed minimum phase CLS FIR filter are lower than the reported methods in literature. Audiogram matching for different filter orders are carried out and is plotted in Figure 5, minimum matching error is obtained for the filter bank structure with filter order 32 (16 coefficients). Hence minimum phase filter derived from CLS FIR filter

Fig 4. Group delay of Minimum phase lowpass filter

with order $n = 32$ is selected for the design of proposed filter bank. High computational cost and long passband group delay are the two important drawbacks of FIR filter banks. This is mainly due to the requirement of large number of multipliers and which in turn is proportional to order of the filter. Here a minimum phase constrained least square FIR filter bank is proposed with low computational complexity and pass band group delay.

Coefficient decimation method (CDM) is used to vary bandwidth and edge frequencies of each filter in the bank in the proposed system. Thus the hearing aid can be dynamically reconfigured, based on the variations in the audiogram of the user. The user can change the gain of each band with the help of an audiologist, based on the audiogram for a particular category of hearing loss. Frequency response of decimated filter obtained from the prototype filter with cut off frequency $f_c = 2$ kHz, by using CDM is plotted in the Figure. 6. Frequency range of operation of a hearing aid is limited and the bandwidths are also narrow, so Coefficient Decimation Method is used in the proposed structure to adjust the bandwidth of filters [19,20]. In CDM, every M^{th} coefficient of the prototype is grouped together by avoiding in between coefficients, so that the passband width of the prototype filter is increased by M times, where M is the integer decimation factor. The stopband attenuation decreases as the value of M increases, hence $M=2$ is selected for the proposed system. A simple 2:1 multiplexer is used in the filter structure to select normal or increased bandwidth filter. The hardware complexity of the CDM structure is very low compared to the reported reconfigurable filter bank structures. The reconfigurable filter bank structure is shown in Fig. 7. Initially, sub band gain of the filter bank is taken as the midpoint value of a specific band of audiogram of a particular hearing loss case and then it is varied to get a minimum

Fig. 5 Matching Errors for different filter orders

overall matching error. In this work, data broadcast structure is used for the filter bank, in which signals are transmitted to all the multipliers at the same time. By this structure, critical path can be reduced without pipelining latches and it will improve clock speed of the system [18]. Critical path represents the minimum time required to process a new sample.

Fig. 6. Minimum phase Filter bank structure

4.1 AUDIOGRAM MATCHING

The filter bandwidths are selected by simulating filters individually in a filter bank for a minimum matching error. The stop band attenuation of the minimum phase CLS FIR Filter is 50 dB. Filter bank performance is evaluated by Matlab software and the gains and frequency bands of filters for audiogram matching are obtained by a number of simulation trials. In this work, the filter bank structures for matching audiogram patterns of mild hearing loss at all frequencies, mild hearing loss at high frequencies and mild to moderate hearing loss at all frequencies are designed. Generally, audible distance is 12 meter for a person with normal hearing whereas this is only 2 meter for a person suffering from mild hearing loss at all frequencies. The audiogram is plotted in Figure 7(a) and Figure 7(b) shows frequency response of the filter bank. Best matching results are obtained by systematically varying the gain magnitudes of 7 bands as shown in Figure 7(c). Matching error is plotted in Figure 10(a) and the maximum matching error obtained is 1.46 dB. Figure 8(a) represents audiogram for mild hearing loss at high frequencies. Frequency response of 7 band filter bank is shown in Figure 8(b), the matching is shown in Figure 8(c), matching error is plotted in Figure 10(b) and the maximum matching error obtained is 1.81 dB. Figure 9(a) represents audiogram of a person suffering from mild to moderate hearing loss at low frequencies. Frequency response of filter bank is shown in Figure 9(b), the matching is shown in Figure 9(c), matching error is plotted in Figure 10(c) and the maximum matching error obtained is 1.86 dB.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 7. Audiogram and experiment results. (a) Audiogram for mild hearing loss at all frequencies, (b) Frequency response of the filter bank, (c) Frequency response of the filter bank after separate gain to each band

(a)

(b)

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Fig. 8. Audiogram and experiment results. (a) Audiogram for mild hearing loss at high frequencies, (b) Frequency response of the filter bank, (c) Frequency response of the filter bank after separate gain to each band

(a)

(b)

©

Fig. 9. Audiogram and experiment results. (a) Audiogram for mild to moderate hearing loss at low frequencies, (b) Frequency response of the filter bank, (c) Frequency response of the filter bank after separate gain to each band

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 10. Matching error for the case of (a) Mild hearing loss at all frequencies, (b) Mild hearing loss at high frequencies, (c) Mild to moderate hearing loss at low frequencies

. Minimum phase CLS FIR filter bank is synthesized using Cadence Encounter(R) RTL Compiler v11.10 software. The area, power and delay reports of Filter bank structure for audiogram matching of mild to moderate hearing loss at all frequencies are given in Table 2.

5. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In the proposed method, hardware requirement for the multiplication operation involved in the filter bank design is reduced considerably. Battery life and size of hearing aid mainly depends on power requirement and area of the filter bank structure used in the device. From the synthesis results of filter bank structures for matching of audiogram for mild to moderate hearing loss at all, it is clear that there is considerable savings in area and power compared to the work [7]. So the proposed filter bank structures require less area and consumes less power, thus reduce hearing aid size and increase the battery life. Comparison of area utilization and power requirement is given in Figure 11. The passband group delay of the minimum phase CLS FIR filter used in the proposed method is lower than reported methods. Area utilization and power requirement increases with increase in number of multipliers per filter in the filter bank structure. Performance comparisons of recently reported filter bank structures which are used for digital hearing aid design is given in the Table 3. Filter bank structure designed by Huang et al.[3] is based on non linear transformation and the number of multipliers/filter required is 187 and the delay is 7.77 ms. Farrow structure based variable bandwidth filter is reported in [4] in which the number of multipliers required per filter is 36 and the delay is 2.06 ms. Here precision of Canonic Signed Digit (CSD) arithmetic is compromised to reduce the multiplier requirement. Fractional interpolation based filter bank structure proposed in [5], uses 84 multipliers/filter and the delay is 13.5ms. In the filter bank based on non uniform modified Discrete Fourier Transform (MDFT) method reported by Sakthivel et al [6], complexity is expressed in terms of the filter order and generally the minimum number of multipliers required for n^{th} order filter is $(n + 1)$.

Table 2 Synthesis results of Filter bank for Mild to Moderate hearing loss at low frequencies

	Mahesh[12]	Proposed
Area (μm^2)	24,99,210.81	17,38,968.74
Power (nW)	513,682,049	312,225,615
Delay (ps)	4919.40	4452

Fig. 11 Comparison of (a) Area (b) Power

Table 3: Performance comparison

Hearing Loss	Method	Multipliers/ Filter	No. of bands	Delay (ms)	Matching Error (dB)
Mild hearing loss at high frequencies	Huang et al.[3]	187	7	7.77	1.65
	Sakthivel Elias [6]	102	10	3.18	2.2
	Amir,Bindiya [5]	74	6	16.5	2.03
	Raghu,Nisha [4]	36	6	2.06	0.98
	Swamy, Alex [9]	72	21	8.67	4.40
	T. Ma, Y. Wei et al. [10]	73	7	7.13	2.34
	Proposed	17	7	0.4935	1.81
Mild hearing loss at all frequencies	Huang et al.[3]	187	7	7.77	1.35
	Sakthivel Elias [6]	56	9	1.75	1.69
	Amir,Bindiya [5]	74	6	12	1.49
	Maresh,Shahana [7]	74	8	2.25	1.82
	Raghu,Nisha [4]	36	6	2.06	2.42
	T. Ma, Y. Wei et al. [10]	73	7	7.13	0.95
	Proposed	17	7	0.4935	1.46
Mild to moderate hearing loss at low frequencies	Huang et al.[3]	187	7	7.77	3.75
	Sakthivel Elias [6]	29	6	0.87	1.87
	Amir,Bindiya [5]	74	6	12	1.48
	Maresh,Shahana [7]	74	7	2.25	1.61
	Raghu,Nisha [4]	36	6	2.06	1.08
	T. Ma, Y. Wei et al. [10]	73	7	7.13	0.98
	Proposed	17	7	0.4935	1.86

In the method proposed by Swamy and Alex [9], delay is less than 10 ms but at the expense of increase in matching error, even greater than 4 dB in some cases. Second order frequency warping based filter bank by T Ma et al. consists of 73 multipliers and seven bands, the delay of the system is 7.13 ms. In the proposed minimum phase CLS FIR filter bank, the number of multipliers per filter is 17 and the maximum pass band group delay is only 0.4935 ms which is the least among the reported methods. Matching error of the proposed structure is within the tolerable limit value of 3 dB. Comparisons shows that the proposed filter bank structure has better performance than the reported methods. Since area, delay and power requirement of the proposed filter bank structure is low, it is suitable for the design of low cost digital hearing aids. The proposed methods can be extended to other common types of hearing loss cases also.

6. CONCLUSION

Power efficiency and compatible size are the two important features of an optimal digital hearing aid. Filter bank structures used in this work require less area and consume low power than the reported methods, hence suitable for the design of compact digital hearing aids. The significant reduction in multipliers per filter enables to reduce hardware requirement considerably in this design. The proposed minimum phase constrained least square finite impulse response filter bank structure show very low pass band group delay and matching error is also within the tolerable limit.

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